

Mixed Ligand Anionic Complexes of Cadmium(II)

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Sixteen mixed ligand anionic complexes of cadmium(II) having the composition $[M]_2[CdCl_4L_2]$, $[M]_2[CdCl_4L']$, $[M]_2[CdCl_4L'']$ and $[M][CdCl_4L''']$, where M=monomethylammonium cation, L=pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, quinoline, 4-aminopyridine, piperidine or thiourea; L'= α -picoline, quinaldine or 2,6-lutidine; L''=ethylenediamine, *o*-phenylenediamine, 1-10-phenanthroline or 2-2'-bipyridine; L'''=oxine or piperidylthiocarbamate, have been synthesized. The compounds of the first and third categories are octahedral and the later two types are penta-coordinated as inferred from elemental analysis, conductance and ir spectral studies.

DIVALENT cadmium forms several four coordinated tetrahedral complexes^{1,2} with a variety of ligands containing O, N, S potential donor sites, involving the use of 5S 5P² hybrid orbitals. Even though the complexes of the composition CdX_4 and CdX_2^+ , where X=Cl⁻ and SCN⁻, have been studied³ in detail potentiometrically, little work has been done to change the stereochemistry of these anionic complexes by reacting with other nitrogen and sulphur donor ligands. To increase the coordination number, particularly to synthesize complexes of coordination number five, we had earlier reported^{4,5} penta-coordinated base-adducts of Zn(II) and Cd(II) dithiocarbamates with N and S donor ligands. Some anionic mixed ligand complexes of Co(II) and Ni(II) exhibiting unusual coordination number have also been reported^{6,7}. This communication describes the preparation and characterisation of sixteen anionic mixed ligand complexes of cadmium(II) containing monomethylammonium chloride and nitrogen and sulphur donor ligands.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A. R. grade. An ethanolic solution of cadmium(II) chloride was treated with an ethanolic solution of monomethylammonium chloride in 1:2 ratio when a white crystalline compound separated out immediately. This was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

The mixed ligand complexes were prepared by adding requisite amount (1:2 ratio) of the nitrogen/sulphur donor ligands to the methanolic solution of di-monomethylammonium tetrachlorocadmium(II). In some cases the compounds were formed immediately and in some cases refluxing was continued for 2 to 3 hr till a clear solution was obtained. A shining needle-shaped crystalline compound separated out on cooling, which was washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Cadmium, nitrogen and chloride were estimated by following the standard methods. The conductance measurements were carried out at room temperature with 10⁻³ M solution in acetone medium using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. IR spectra of the complexes were recorded on KBr phase using Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Relevant analytical and conductance data are given in Table I.

Results and Discussion

Analysis and conductance data indicate that the complexes have the following composition: $[M]_2[CdCl_4L_2]$, $[M]_2[CdCl_4L']$, $[M]_2[CdCl_4L'']$ and $[M][CdCl_4L''']$, where M=monomethylammonium cation; L=pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, quinoline, 4-aminopyridine, piperidine or thiourea; L'= α -picoline, quinaldine or 2,6-lutidine; L''=ethylenediamine, *o*-phenylenediamine, 1-10-phenanthroline or 2-2'-bipyridine and L'''=oxine or piperidylthiocarbamate.

All the compounds have high melting points and are white, greyish-white to yellow in colour, soluble in acetone in which medium the Δ_M values are around 230 mhos cm² indicating 2:1 electrolytic nature of the first fourteen complexes. The Δ_M values for the last two complexes are ~115 mhos cm² indicating them to be 1:1 electrolytes.

Study of ir spectra is quite informative. Absorption bands are noticed at 930(vs), 980(s), 1260(vs), 1410(s), 1485(s) and 3150(s) cm⁻¹, characteristic of the bands due to monomethylammonium chloride, modified due to complexation. Most of the absorption bands due to free sulphur and nitrogen donor ligands have been modified in the anionic mixed ligand complexes, indicating their bonding to the cadmium(II) ion. In sodium salt of piperidylthiocarbamate, the appearance of bands at 840 and 1260 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to thiol (C-S) and thiocarbonyl (C=S) absorption bands, respectively. In Cd(II) complexes, shifting of these bands to lower

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT AND CONDUCTANCE DATA

Compound	m.p. °C	%Cd		%N		%Cl		Λ_M mhos cm ²
		Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (Py) ₂]	>250	23.52	23.69	11.72	11.80	29.47	29.77	240.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (β -Pic) ₂]	>250	22.17	22.46	11.12	11.19	28.08	28.12	230.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (γ -Pic) ₂]	>250	22.29	22.46	11.07	11.19	28.02	28.12	245.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (4-AP) ₂]	>250	22.16	22.28	16.67	16.65	27.92	28.01	225.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (Q) ₂]	>250	19.32	19.56	9.68	9.74	24.35	24.60	220.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (tu) ₂]	>250	33.81	23.91	11.85	11.93	30.06	30.15	215.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (Pip) ₂]	>250	22.95	23.10	11.43	11.51	28.95	29.04	240.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (en) ₂]	>250	29.75	29.89	14.72	14.87	32.18	32.35	220.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (<i>o</i> -Ph.D) ₂]	>250	26.27	26.48	13.15	13.19	26.48	26.54	230.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (1,10-Ph) ₂]	>250	22.51	22.64	11.16	11.28	28.37	28.46	225.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (2,2'-Bi) ₂]	>250	23.62	23.79	11.79	11.85	29.83	29.90	220.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (α -Pic) ₂]	>250	27.35	27.52	10.17	10.28	34.39	34.48	235.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (Quin) ₂]	>250	24.27	24.46	9.08	9.14	30.58	30.74	225.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (2,6-Lut) ₂]	>250	26.43	26.67	9.78	9.96	33.29	33.34	220.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (OX) ₂]	>250	28.48	28.57	7.05	7.11	27.95	28.00	115.00
[M] ₂ [CdCl ₄ (P-dtc) ₂]	>250	27.32	27.45	6.79	6.83	25.82	25.89	110.00

M = monomethylammonium cation, Py = pyridine, α -Pic = α -picoline, β -Pic = β -picoline, γ -Pic = γ -picoline, Q = quinoline, 4-AP = 4-aminopyridine, tu = thiourea, Pip = piperidine, en = ethylenediamine, *o*-Ph.D = *o*-phenylenediamine, 1,10-Ph = 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-Bi = 2,2'-bipyridine, Quin = quinaldine, 2,6-Lut = 2,6-lutidine, OX = oxine, P-dtc = piperidylthiocarbamate.

frequency region occurs, indicating coordination through both sulphur atoms. $\nu(C-O)$ and $\nu(C=N)$ of oxine appear at 1200 cm⁻¹ and 1590 cm⁻¹, respectively, indicating the coordination of oxine moiety to the Cd(II) ion through hydroxyl oxygen and ring nitrogen atom.

From the analysis, conductance and ir spectral studies, the compounds of the first and the third categories are octahedral in configuration. The compounds of the second category are presumed to be penta-coordinated because of the mono-adduct formation favoured by the sterically hindered nitrogen donor ligands like α -picoline, quinaldine and 2,6-lutidine. The compounds of the fourth category are also penta-coordinated as inferred from analysis, conductance and ir spectral data. In view of the

spherical nature of Cd(II) ion and absence of crystal field effects, this possibility is not entirely unexpected. However, X-ray crystallographic study will reveal the exact stereochemistry of these complexes.

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